

MedVetKlebs deliverable D-JRP11-2.2

December 2019 (month 24)

Methods:

In the multicentric study (five sampling centers involved), a total of 305 samples were analyzed, with 160 from chicken meat and 145 from ready-to-eat salads (**Table 1**). Chicken meat showed a prevalence of Kp twice as high as salads (58% versus 30%, accordingly to ZKIR qPCR results). A total of 131 Kp isolates were recovered.

Results:

Table 1. Comparison between ZKIR qPCR and culture results obtained using samples from chicken meat and salads collected by five partners.

Source	No. of samples	qPCR positive samples (%)	Culture positive samples (%)
Chicken meat	160	93 (58%)	83 (52%)
Salads	145	43 (30%)	30 (21%)
Total	305	136 (45%)	113 (37%)